

Agro2Circular

D.8.6 Toolkit of Guidelines and Training Materials (Draft)

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1 Technical references

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* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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3 List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU)
CE	Circular Economy
COI	Community of Interest
CEBMs	Business models for Circular Economy innovations
CCAA	Autonomous Communities
CSO	Civil Society Organisation

4 Executive summary

This is the **first draft of D.8.6 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials**, a set of didactic materials and analysis of lessons learnt in order to be transferred and shared with other projects, initiatives and institutions working on community-based research, participatory methods and education for environmental issues or local climate change mitigation as well as those targeting cluster and industry about circular business models, financing and regulatory issues: CEBMs, financing & regulatory issues, public engagement, circular economy and environmental education, Best Practices book, training plan for local actors/education services. The content of this document is therefore fed by the activities carried out in other activities, mainly: T7.1 (Public Engagement); T7.3 (Environmental Assessment); T7.4 (Social and economic analysis); T7.5 (Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level) and T8.3 (Communication and engagement at local and regional level).

This deliverable constitutes a first outline and the main methodological choices made for the development of the final version of the deliverable (D.8.7. Toolkit of guidelines and training materials, to be delivered on month 35).

5 Introduction: objectives & relations with other tasks and outputs

This deliverable is framed within the overall objective of **WP8 - A2C outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, training & policy recommendations**. Thus, it is part of the activities aimed at widespreading the project results and engaging stakeholders, while raising awareness and knowledge about circular economy and innovations produced by A2C.

More specifically, this is the first outcome of the **Task 8.6 Training, knowledge transfer and guidelines/recommendations to promote A2C circular model. (M9- M36)**, aiming at delivering specific resources and open learning materials to contribute to the promotion of the model, taking into account the facilitators and barriers identified in WP7. The task includes the elaboration of an autonomous training plan for local actors and education services for local communities and training modules/guidelines for EU stakeholders to better implement/transfer the knowledge acquired during the project and all lessons learnt.

Two deliverables will be developed from this task: D8.6 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Draft), the object of the present document, which includes a first outline of some of the materials/guidelines to be developed in the framework of Task 8.6; and **D8.7 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Final)**, to be delivered in month 35, as a developed and final version of the contents foreseen in Task 8.6, as shown in the following figure:

Therefore, the deliverable contains a set of didactic materials intended to be shared with various actors and institutions for education/training/dissemination of circular economy

knowledge and competences. This includes different target groups, ranging from non-higher education institutions (schools, secondary schools, vocational schools) to higher education institutions (graduates, master and doctoral students) including the general population, the industry, Civil Society Organisations and Public Administrations.

The different thematic areas of the deliverable are the following:

1. Business models for Circular Economy innovations (CEBMs)
2. Financing and regulatory issues related to Circular Economy
3. Environmental education for the youth
4. Guidelines for fostering public engagement in Circular Economy projects and environmental community-based activities.
5. Industry mentoring programme for the generation of innovative results-oriented ideas to respond to circular business challenges.
6. Good practice directory for Circular Economy in the agrifood sector

Given that some of the activities, from which the essential information/lessons learnt to produce the materials will be obtained. have not yet been carried out, this document presents the necessary synergies with the work of other WPs, as well as the main contents and primary target groups of the materials to be developed. Also, as some of the thematic areas require specific methodological preparation beyond the conversion of the project results into didactic and training materials, a brief methodological description of the activities is given in the relevant thematic blocks (8. Guidelines for public engagement in Circular Economy projects and environmental community-based activities, and the evaluation system proposed by UVEG in section 10. Industry Mentoring Programme proposed by PRIMA). In section 9. Environmental Education, examples of available materials for different topics are also shown, while in sections 10. Industry Mentoring Programme and 11. Good practice directory for Circular Economy, a first draft of these activities is provided.

D8.6. Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Draft) (Month 18)	First draft and outline of the work to be undertaken.
D8.7. Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Final) (Month 35)	Development of the activities and final version of the materials

6 Business models for Circular Economy innovations (CEBMs)

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

*“It will be designed and executed an autonomous but comprehensive training plan for local actors and education services for local communities and training modules/ guidelines for EU stakeholders to better implement/transfer the knowledge acquired during the project and all lessons learnt, contributing to both a more effective development of circular solutions and to foster the communities’ environmental awareness and sustainable habits, business and co-creation. **Among others: a) business models for circular economy innovations.**”*

The Circular Economy action plan acknowledges the need to support the skills and job creation to accelerate the transition to a circular economy. Likewise, the EU SME strategy has included among the barriers for these companies to ‘going green’ the lack of technical and managerial knowledge, skills and information; this was also stressed by some of the partners in previous workshops performed in the project. Therefore, this chapter will cover the design of training plans for companies on business models for circular economy innovations.

<p>Relation with other partners and WPs</p>	<p>WP1- CETEC Task 5.1 A2C Data Integration System (DIS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Big data statistics and indicators for valuation of raw materials - Blockchain as tool for traceability along value chains <p>WP6 – UB. Task 6.4. A2C business cases and financing (M12 to M36). Among the activities to be carried out by UB within the framework of this task are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification and categorization of circular economy business models through desk research - Development of a Circular Economy modelling framework - Support partners in the creation of new circular economy business models - Report on financing mechanisms to support business model replication. - Natural Capital Assessment on the solutions demonstrated in the project to improve the circular business models, identify strategies to manage possible risks and identify new revenue streams. <p>The most relevant desk research and lessons learned from this work will be incorporated into the training materials.</p>
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	<p>WP7 – UB. Task 7.4 Social and economic analysis UB performs a Life Cycle Costing analysis (the process of compiling all costs that the owner or producer of an asset will incur over its lifespan) in the framework of WP7 evaluation related activities.</p> <p>The main lessons learned from the results will also be incorporated into the materials.</p>
<p>Materials to be developed/ target groups</p>	<p>Guidelines, training pathways, designed practical activities and materials (slides) for: Secondary schools, Business schools, industry, environmental entrepreneurs, etc.</p>

While guidelines and reports will be developed for all of the above target groups, some examples of materials for specific target groups are presented in the following sections.

The general schedule of activities is shown in Figure 2:

Timeline	2023												2024								
Activities	ma	apr	ma	jun	julv	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	ma	apr	ma	jun	julv	aug	sep		
1. Preparation phase																					
Coordination with UB for the thematic development of the materials.																					
2. Materials development																					
Development of materials not dependent on UB research results																					
Development of materials dependent on UB's research results.																					

Figure 2 - Schedule of activities - Business Models CE

In subsequent phases of the project, the most appropriate materials will be selected, and their syllabus will be developed:

6.1 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for primary and secondary schools.

<p>Case study of a company</p>	<p>Students research on a company using circular economy principles in its business models. The students analyse how the company’s business model works, what the benefits are and how it is different from other business models.</p>
<p>Role-playing game</p>	<p>Students take on different roles in a circular economy business model, such as a waste collector, manufacturer of recycled products or distributor/end seller. This way, students can learn about how the material flow works and how new products can be created from used materials.</p>
<p>Brainstorming new business models</p>	<p>In this activity, students work in groups to identify sustainability problems in their community and then come up</p>

	with ideas for new business models that can address those problems using circular economy principles.
Creating a business prototype	Students work in teams to develop a business prototype using circular economy principles. This activity would involve the creation of a business plan for a company collecting and recycling food waste, linking it to the A2C model.

6.2 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for institutions of higher education.

Case study analysis	Students analyse case studies of companies using circular economy business models in different industries, such as agrifood. From the analysis of these cases, students could assess the effectiveness and feasibility of these business models, identify barriers to their implementation and discuss opportunities for improvement.
Market research	Students conduct market research to identify circular economy-based business opportunities in a specific industry. From the results of the research, students could develop a detailed business plan for a new company using circular economy principles.
Hackathon	Students participate in a circular economy hackathon, where they work in teams to develop new business models based on circular economy principles. Students would have the opportunity to collaborate with other students and experts in the field to develop creative and sustainable solutions based on the examples proposed by A2C.
Business innovation project	Students develop an innovative business model using circular economy principles. The project could include the identification of business opportunities, defining a market strategy, developing a sustainable supply chain and assessing the environmental and economic impact of the proposed business models, based on the evaluation work developed in WP7 of A2C.

6.3 Syllabus for a circular economy course for undergraduate students in Business Administration

A tentative syllabus is presented to which theoretical content will be incorporated and whose outline will be updated once relevant results are obtained in WP6 and WP7:

I. Introduction to the circular economy

- Basic concepts and principles of the circular economy
- Differences between circular economy and linear economy

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- Advantages and benefits of the circular economy

II. Circular economy business models

- Analysis of case studies of companies using circular economy business models in different industries
- Identification of business opportunities based on the circular economy in different industries
- Development of business plans for new circular economy business models

III. New business models based on the circular economy.

- Identification of emerging business opportunities in the circular economy, such as recycling of construction materials or e-waste management
- Development of business plans for new business models based on circular economy principles.

IV. Financing schemes for circular economy projects

- Identification of different financing schemes for circular economy projects, such as grants, loans and investment funds.
- Assessment of the advantages and disadvantages of each financing scheme
- Developing a financing plan for a circular economy project

V. Practical applications of the circular economy

- Visiting companies that use circular economy principles in their business model
- Practical circular economy projects, such as designing a waste recycling system in a company or identifying circular economy business opportunities in a given industry.
- DIS & blockchain in Circular Economy

VI. Legal and regulatory aspects of the circular economy

- Legal and regulatory framework of the circular economy at national and international level
- Assessment of the legal and regulatory barriers for the implementation of circular economy business models.

VII. Assessing and measuring the impact of the circular economy

- Environmental and economic impact assessment of circular economy business models
- Identification of key performance indicators to measure the success of a circular economy business model

VIII. Conclusions and final reflections

- Review of the key concepts and issues addressed in the course
- Reflections on the importance of the circular economy in the future of business and society
- Evaluation of the impact of the course on the students' training

7 Financing and regulatory issues related to Circular Economy

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

*“It will be designed and executed an autonomous but comprehensive training plan for local actors and education services for local communities and training modules/ guidelines for EU stakeholders to better implement/transfer the knowledge acquired during the project and all lessons learnt, contributing to both a more effective development of circular solutions and to foster the communities’ environmental awareness and sustainable habits, business and co-creation. **Among others: b) financing and regulatory issues related to CE”***

Therefore, although the two matters are connected, **regulatory issues** must be distinguished from those related to **financing schemes**, as the target groups of the materials may be different in each case. In any case, this does not preclude that some of the materials produced include both types of topics.

<p>Relation with other partners and WPs</p>	<p>The contents from which the proposed materials will be prepared will be obtained from the following tasks:</p> <p>WP7 – UVEG Sub-Task 7.5.2. Regulatory, standardisation and political relevant factors at European level. Comprehensive research into regulatory and political factors enabling or limiting the adoption of the A2C systemic solution will be carried out in order to elaborate guidelines, able to contribute to replication and scalability according to the factors identified. It entails the definition of the regulatory frameworks, public context (including public funding -EURA-) and standardisation activities (addressed at Task 8.5).</p> <p>WP7 – EURA Sub-Task 7.5.3. Financing schemes linked to the business models generated. This task explores the financing ecosystem enabling the adoption of territorial circular solutions at regional/national/EU levels, which involves the collection and management of the data about green public procurement and the analysis of good practices of financing tools for A2C.</p> <p>WP6 – UB, CJM & INFO Task 6.4. A2C business cases and financing (M12 to M36). In this task, CJM is in charge of assessing and considering financing mechanisms to support business model replications, stressing the</p>
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	suitability, major opportunities and their associated risks. INFO contributes to this task with knowledge related to public funding mechanisms. UB is in charge of the identification of links with natural capital, the impacts of operations on natural capital and the extent of dependencies , identify strategies to manage possible risks and identify new revenue streams.
Materials to be developed/ target groups	<p><u>Regulatory issues:</u> Materials (academic curriculum + slides) oriented to undergraduate (environmental administrative law), masters (environmental law) and doctoral studies. Materials oriented to the agrifood and plastic industry. Integration of these issues in materials on the topic of Circular Economy to be implemented in schools (secondary schools, high schools).</p> <p><u>Financing schemes:</u> Materials (academic curriculum + slides) oriented to undergraduate studies (business administration and management, law), master's degree (business administration and management, MBA) and PhD. Materials oriented to agrifood and plastics industry, entrepreneurs and professionals.</p>

While guidelines and reports will be developed for all of the above target groups, some examples of materials for specific target groups are presented in the following sections. In subsequent phases of the project, the most appropriate materials will be selected, and their syllabus will be developed.

The general schedule of activities is shown in Figure 3:

Timeline	2023												2024							
	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep	
1. Preparation phase																				
Coordination with EURA for thematic development of materials related to financing schemes																				
UVEG's own desk research on regulatory issues																				
2. Materials development																				
Development of materials on regulatory issues																				
Development of materials on financing schemes																				
Peer review and submission of deliverable																				

Figure 3 - Schedule of activities - Regulatory & Financing

The following are the main topics around which the materials will address. As the related WP7 Tasks develop, more topics and sub-topics will be included:

7.1 Main contents related to regulatory issues.

1. Regulation of the Circular Economy at EU level

- a. European Green Deal
- b. European Semester
- c. Circular Economy Action Plan COM/2020/98 final. Action Plan and first Circular Economy Package (pieces of legislation 2022 & 2023):
 - i. The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation;

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- ii. The Review of the Construction Product Regulation;
- iii. The EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles;
- iv. The empowering Consumers for a Green Transition legislation.
- d. Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives
- e. Directive 2006/66/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 September 2006 on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators and repealing Directive 91/157/EEC
- f. Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)
- g. Directive 2001/81/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2001 on national emission ceilings for certain atmospheric pollutants

2. Regulation of the Circular Economy at national level (Spain)

- a. Spanish Circular Economy Strategy
- b. Derived pieces of legislation
- c. Law 7/2022 on Waste and Contaminated Soil for a circular economy

3. Regulation of the Circular Economy at regional level (different CCAA, especially Murcia region)

- a. Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia 2030
- b. Autonomous Regions' laws and legislative initiatives at the preliminary draft stage in the various Spanish Autonomous Regions

4. Regulation of the Circular Economy at municipal and provincial level.

- a. Local strategy for circular economy (Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces)
- b. Local strategy for circular economy
- c. Good practices

The materials will include lessons learnt from the project and, especially, a reference to the regulatory barriers that may hinder a) the implementation of regional Circular Economy models such as the one proposed by A2C; and b) the achievement of a true circular economy at EU level. Tentatively:

- Lack of definitions and/or gaps in legislation
- Unclear definitions of targets in legislation
- Outdated definitions for the numerical limits in regulations
- Lagging or incomplete implementation or enforcement of legislation

- Different and conflicting national implementations of legislation
- Potential conflicts between regulations (hygiene, food waste, livestock hygiene, nutrient transportation, etc.)
- Digital tools to overcome regulatory issues: the case of A2C DIS for waste traceability.

7.2 Main contents related to financing schemes.

1. Financing schemes for Circular Economy

- a. EU funds: Horizon Europe, Regional Policy Support, Interreg Europe, LIFE, Single Market Programme, Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP)
- b. Incentives
- c. Global Opportunities
- d. Financial institutions and other for-profit initiatives: European Investment Bank (EIB), Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE), European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)
- e. Asset Management Firms
- f. Crowdfunding
- g. Public Financing Schemes at regional and national level
- h. Private Financing schemes & Agro2Circular Business Models

2. Good Practices

- a. CIRCWASTE (Finland)
- b. URBIOFIN (Greece)
- c. EIB Financed Projects (Italy, Romania, France)
- d. De Clique (The Netherlands)
- e. Green Public Procurement Good Practices

8 Guidelines for public engagement in Circular Economy projects and environmental community-based activities.

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

“A set of guidelines for fostering public engagement in circular economy projects will be also generated by conducting a joint reflection on the ways for fostering effective communication & public engagement for circular economy projects and environmental community-based initiatives, contributing to the know-how and the literature at EU about participatory and co-creation frameworks applied to environmental fields. The elaboration of these guidelines will require the participation of stakeholders from the quadruple helix in workshops, focus groups and DELPHI studies.”

The guidelines for fostering public engagement in circular economy initiatives will therefore be developed based on the information collected through different qualitative research methods implemented with key informants that are part of the quadruple helix of stakeholders (Public Administration, Research/Academia, Industry, Civil Society Organisations and general citizenship).

<p>Relation with other partners and WPs</p>	<p>WP7 – KVC. Task 7.1. Public Engagement and community-based schemes for sustainable systemic circular economy (M1- M36).</p> <p>The work carried out by KVC in the mapping and set up of the project's stakeholder panel is crucial for the development of the research activities. KVC has provided input to UVEG for the development of this deliverable and will be a relevant partner to rely on for the continued development and recruitment of stakeholders for this activity.</p>
<p>Materials to be developed/ target groups</p>	<p>Guidelines in the form of policy recommendations; materials for courses in political science and sociology; materials for use in schools (combined with existing materials on the general topic of circular economy)</p>

Thus, section 8.1 shows the main methodological options that will be implemented in subsequent phases of the project, and section 8.2 shows the stakeholders from whom information will be collected, as well as the timing of the activities leading to obtain the guidelines:

8.1 Methodology

Four different techniques will be considered, depending on the capacity to recruit and coordinate members of different stakeholder groups for specific events. Two of these techniques are foreseen in the Grant Agreement (Focus Groups and Delphi panels), and

two others are not, but are "back-up" techniques that may be used if necessary (in-depth interviews and communities of interest):

1. **Focus Groups:** focus groups are an appropriate tool for research on public opinion¹ as it allows for the study of a variety of social profiles, while producing focused- in depth data on a given topic². Also, in contrast to individual interviews, participants in focus-groups contrast their individual views with others' perspectives in a low-structured setting. Thus, focus-groups offer the opportunity to analyse closely how people collectively construct their discursive positions, marking their agreements and disagreements³. Focus groups are the most appropriate technique to use with the following stakeholder groups: Public Administration, Industry, Civil Society Organisations.
2. **Delphi panels:** Delphi panels are typically applicable when there is limited evidence, when the existing evidence is contradictory in the specific topic of interest, and/or where advantage could be realised in the collective subjective judgement of experts⁴. The basic design involves assembling groups of experts without concern for geography, and who then reply to a number of "rounds" involving response to a specific question or questions through e-mail. After each round, participants receive feedback of the group response which typically takes the form of points of agreement listed in order of most- to least often mentioned⁵. Therefore, this method will be used with research/academic stakeholders.
3. **In-depth interviews:** an interview is an important qualitative research method in which the researcher collects data directly from the participants. Mostly paired with other research methods like survey, focus group etc., interviews are significant in unfolding opinions, experiences, values and various other aspects of the population under study. Interviews are always goal oriented⁶. Specifically, in-depth interviews are mostly long-duration, face-to-face, interviews conducted to achieve desired goals. In-depth interview also known as one-on-one is a method of extracting more detailed information or deep understanding of a subject or concept⁷. Thus, in-depth interviews with all stakeholder groups will be considered depending on the circumstances of time availability and coordination.

¹ M. Delli Carpini and B. Williams, "The method is the message: Focus groups as a method of social, psychological, and political inquiry," in *Research in Micropolitics: New Directions in Political Psychology*, M. Delli Carpini, L. Huddie, and R. Shapiro, Eds. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, 1994, pp. 57-85.

² D. Morgan, "Focus groups," *Annual Review of Sociology*, pp. 129-152, 1996.

³ J. Kitzinger, "The methodology of focus groups: the importance of interaction between research participants," *Sociology of Health & Illness*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 103-121, Jan. 1994.

⁴ J. R. Avella, "Delphi Panels: Research Design, Procedures, Advantages, and Challenges," in *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, vol. 11, pp. 305-321, 2016, doi: 10.28945/3522.

⁵ H. A. Linstone and M. Turoff, Eds., *The Delphi method: Techniques and applications*. [Online]. Available: <http://is.njit.edu/pubs/delphibook/delphibook.pdf>, 2002.

⁶ S. Kvale, *Interviews: An Introduction to Qualitative Research Interviewing*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 1996..

⁷ A. Adams and A. L. Cox, "Questionnaires, in-depth interviews and focus groups," in *Research Methods for Human Computer Interaction*, P. Cairns and A. L. Cox, Eds. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2008, pp. 17–34.

4. **Communities of inquiry:** Interviews and focus groups are very robust techniques for obtaining qualitative information for research purposes. However, interviews can also reinforce existing power relations between researchers and respondents, especially if the respondents come from vulnerable or marginalised communities⁸. Although A2C regional stakeholder panel involved for the activities does not foresee it, there may be the option of having a group of local citizens (not necessarily integrated in any CSO) whose composition may be heterogeneous (it may include some members of population groups traditionally considered as vulnerable or disempowered). If this is the case, the use of the Community of Interest (Col) methodology will be considered: Col takes the form of group dialogue. In response to a difficult question, a group of individuals create a community where they participate in a process of critical examination of the key concepts behind the question by drawing on their own experiences, learning with each other by listening to what others say—a process whereby an intersubjective agreement on the resolution of the question emerges⁹. This differs from the traditional focus group in the fact that interviewees, not interviewers, put questions to each other in a reciprocal way to gain a clearer understanding of one another's position. This means that, in Col, participants serve as quasi-interviewers. While Col is a form of group interview, this unique feature can further contribute to making the interview process more inclusive¹⁰.

The following is a battery of questions suitable for use with each stakeholder group covered in this activity, which is subject to further modification and refinement:

Questions Associations/citizenship.

- Why are you involved in circular economy initiatives?
- How can a person get started in circular economy projects?
- What do you think is the biggest problem when it comes to encouraging the general public to join this type of projects?
- Is there sufficient support from the administration?
- Do you consider that you have lost or gained quality of life by undertaking sustainable initiatives?
- What particular knowledge do you think you need to have in order to start collecting and reducing food waste?
- Do you think you separate your waste properly, and in how many parts do you do it?
- Do you think there is enough information available about where the collection points are located (not only paper, glass, organic, but also batteries, oil, sewage, etc.)?

⁸ C. Auerswald, A. A. Piatt, and A. Mirzazadeh, "Research with Disadvantaged, Vulnerable, and/or Marginalized Adolescents," *Innocenti Research Briefs*, UNICEF Office of Research, Florence, 2017.

⁹ K. Nishiyama, "Community of Inquiry," in *Research Methods in Deliberative Democracy*, S. A. Ercan et al., Eds. Oxford, UK: Oxford Academic, Nov. 17, 2022.

¹⁰ K. Nishiyama, "Using the Community of Inquiry for Interviewing Children: Theory and Practice," *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 553–564, 2018.

- Do you think that digital tools could help the implementation of Circular Economy?

Questions for business/industry

- What kind of barriers can you encounter when trying to make the transition to a more sustainable production model?
- What kind of public initiatives (subsidies, training programmes, creating taxes on non-recycling, etc.) could help companies to shift towards a much more circular production (waste collection, direct super-recycling, investment in R&D, etc.)?
- Do you consider that implementing more sustainable methods of production adds value to your products?
- What uses do you make of your products beyond sales, and of the waste derived from their production (sales, self-consumption, energy, fertiliser, animal feed, etc.)?
- Do you separate your production waste?
- What are the main difficulties in separating the different types of waste for collection?
- Do you think you separate your waste properly and in how many parts do you separate it?
- Do you think that the use of used materials for suprarecycling is an improvement, or a competitive disadvantage compared to other companies in the sector?
- Do you think that the differentiation of labelling between sustainable and non-sustainable products means that consumers are more interested in the former?
- How do you think that new consumers can be attracted to sustainable products?
- With a higher profitability of these (circular economy) production processes, would more sectors/companies switch to this type of production, or are there other disadvantages?
- Do you think that the use of digital tools could help your company fulfil regulations posed by Circular Economy? / Do you think that the use of digital tools could help your company find new valorisation routes for the materials you use or the waste you generate?

Questions University/Academia.

- What are the main barriers to be faced in order to realise circular economy initiatives?
- Do you consider that there is sufficient information among the different actors to carry out these processes?
- Do you think that there are sufficient means to be able to carry out major circular economy initiatives?
- Is a major transformation of the production model necessary to carry out circular economy measures or can small changes be made within the current model?
- Is there clear legislation on the circular economy or are there some shortcomings in the European legislative system?
- What do you think would be the optimal way to implement these initiatives?

- Do you think that the policies being implemented are in line with the objectives of creating more and more circular economy initiatives?
- What do you think is the motivation for citizens to get involved in these projects?
- And what do you think is the reason why citizens decide not to get involved?
- What are the main training or education gaps you find related to circular economy?

Questions Public Administration.

- What do you think is the biggest shortcoming of Public Administrations when it comes to carrying out circular/sustainable economy projects? (Lack of legislation, lack of funds, lack of participants, no interest from politicians because it does not bring electoral benefits, lack of training for technicians, lack of training for private agents, etc.).
- Do you consider that the socio-political context is favourable for the implementation of measures towards a more circular economy?
- What do you think are the possible risks or disadvantages of implementing this type of initiative?
- Do you think it is possible to promote such initiatives in small/medium sized municipalities?
- What do you think is the optimal way to carry out these public policies (through specialised companies, European projects, regional projects, municipal actions, etc.)?
- Do you consider that there is good access to data from other projects in order to be able to adapt these functional models to one's own territory of action?
- Is there a willingness on the part of the different actors (academia, private sector, citizens) to implement these actions?
- What are the priorities when carrying out a sustainable economy project (economic expenditure, energy expenditure, creating new production models, improving the environmental situation, etc.)?
- Do you think that the use of digital tools could help public administrations to ensure the fulfilment of circular Economy regulations?

Possible refinements and modifications to the above questions shall be made on the basis of, inter alia, the following bibliography:

- Danae Manika, Eleni Iacovidou, Ana Canhoto, Eujin Pei, Khanh Mach, Capabilities, opportunities and motivations that drive food waste disposal practices: A case study of young adults in England, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 370, 2022 ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133449>
- Joensuu, K., Hartikainen, H., Karppinen, S. et al. Developing the collection of statistical food waste data on the primary production of fruit and vegetables. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 28, 24618-24627 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09908-5>

- Sani, Daniela, Sara Picone, Augusto Bianchini, Fabio Fava, Patricia Guarnieri, and Jessica Rossi. 2021. "An Overview of the Transition to a Circular Economy in Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy Considering Technological, Legal-Regulatory and Financial Points of View: A Case Study." *Sustainability* 13, no. 2: 596. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020596>
- Binxian Gu, Yanbin Yao, Huimin Hang, Yulin Wang, Renfu Jia, Lingxuan Liu, Hui Ling, Xinyi Tang, Haijie Zhang, Zhiwei Wu, Yongxiang Wu, Takeshi Fujiwara, Yanchao Bai, Promoting Chinese urban residents' participation in source separation and recycling, *Waste Management*, Volume 139, 2022, Pages 290-299, ISSN 0956-053X <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.12.032>
- Allison, Ayşe Lisa, Fabiana Lorencatto, Susan Michie, and Mark Miodownik. 2021. "Barriers and Enablers to Buying Biodegradable and Compostable Plastic Packaging" *Sustainability* 13, no. 3: 1463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031463>

8.2 Stakeholder panels and planning

Below are the stakeholders whose participation has been confirmed at the project events and who will therefore be contacted for participation in the focus groups, interviews and Delphi panels:

A) Stakeholder panel: Regional level

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Level	Description
Public Administration	Europa Direct Region of Murcia-Directorate General of the European Union (Regional level)	Competences in EU relations by providing an information service on EU institutions, policies and opportunities for EU citizens.
Public Administration	Alhama City Council (Municipal level)	Municipality Major.
Industry	AEMA (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia)	Environmental Businesses Association Region of Murcia. Including waste management, environmental consultancy, environmental quality, etc.
Research/Academia	Water eco-efficiency chair (Regional level)	University of Murcia
Research/Academia	CETENMA (Regional level)	Environment research centre (private non for profit)
Research/Academia	Molina Vocational Training Centre (CIFEA) (Regional level)	Organisation of complementary and specialised training courses and actions, of regional, national and international scope, with the aim of updating and perfecting the technical skills of professionals in the sector.

Civil Society	Ambiente Europeo (Regional level)	Specialised in CE and pollutions issues, collaboration with industries
Civil Society	Association of street market vendors (Regional level)	Association of street vendors of the Region of Murcia

The list may be reinforced with additional actors, such as local civil society organisations, recruited through community-based schemes in T7.1.2

B) Stakeholder panel: EU level

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Country	Description
Consumer Association	Unione Nazionale Consumatori Umbria (Italy)	Unione Nazionale Consumatori (UNC) is the first consumer association in Italy
Industry	Digiotouch (Estonia)	ICT innovations and services through its participation in EU Horizon 2020 projects and strong in-house R&D. The company is experienced with Standard Development on IoT, Web of Things, and Digital Transformation
Industry	FILSE SPA (Italy)	Consultancy LIGURIA supports region (public administrations) in development of policies and interventions
Industry	Agrotransilvania Cluster (Romania)	Technology transfer centre of RDI in agro-industrial field at national level.
Research/Academia	Veltha (Italy)	Research centre; development of Policies for Sustainable Development and Social Innovation
Research/Academia	Aalborg University (Denmark)	Packaging technology, packaging machinery and press-forming, heat sealing and converting of fibre-based materials.
Public Administration	Municipality of Nea Smyrni (Greece)	Deputy Mayor.

The general schedule of activities is shown in Figure 4:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101036838.

Timeline	2023												2024							
Activities	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep	
1. Preparation phase																				
Methodology refinement																				
Contacts and/or further recruitment																				
2. Implementation phase																				
Implementation of activities																				
3. Guidelines development																				
Deliverable preparation																				
Peer review and submission																				

Figure 4 - Schedule of activities - Guidelines for fostering citizen engagement.

9 Environmental Education for the youth

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

“MSc and PhD students will be involved through receiving additional training, aligned with the project objectives, scope and results, within their formal education context (e.g., Master classes) thanks to the participation of academic entities within the project. However, the most important and relevant part considering the aims of A2C is the integration of formal and non-formal education for graduates, MSc students and PhD researchers and ESR. (...) During the project lifecycle and in line with the contextual determinants of each site, activities for youth will be designed, always aimed at raising the bonds between academic, business, and decision-making entities. Key topics will be:

- Agrifood, plastics and the circular economy*
- General considerations and context of the circular economy*
- The A2C results and outcomes*
- Environmental-responsive entrepreneurship: Clusters and sectoral initiatives; Synergies; Academic careers, entrepreneurship and intellectual exploitation*
- Specific seminars and workshops on key outputs from the A2C project depending on each country/partner.”*

<p>Relation with other partners and WPs</p>	<p>WP8 – PRIMA, PROEX, AGRO, KVC, ICONS, CARM, CJM, INFO.</p> <p>Task 8.3 Communication and engagement at local and regional level.</p> <p>Coordination with partners who are conducting presentations/workshops at different levels for collaboration and co-design of specific materials. I.e., 4 presentations have already been given in high schools, and PRIMA is already performing a course to create a videogame among secondary students: Task 8.3 (2) Regional contests for scholars aimed to spread the circular economy approach and fostering their involvement in these practices. Students will dare to solve a problem related to the sustainability of a product/processing waste. Best solutions will receive recognition at an organised event.</p> <p>For the introduction of the results and outcomes of the A2C project, UVEG will coordinate with ICONS in order to ensure that the preparation of materials complies with IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) regulations.</p>
<p>Materials to be developed/ target groups</p>	<p>Designed practical activities (such as role-playing games, scenarios, crosswords, etc.), course outlines and slideshows. For non-higher education institutions (schools, secondary schools, compulsory secondary education, baccalaureate, etc.).</p>

The general schedule of activities is shown in Figure 5:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101036838.

Timeline	2023												2024						
Activities	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep	oct	nov	dec	jan	feb	ma	apr	ma	jun	july	aug	sep
1. Preparation phase																			
Coordination with partners on 8.3 for needs assessment																			
2. Materials development																			
Development of materials																			
Peer review and submission of deliverable																			

Figure 5 - Schedule of activities - educational materials

Thus, each of the topics in which the materials will be developed are described below:

9.1 Agrifood, plastics and the Circular Economy

On this regard, task 8.3 foresees the preparation of materials to be taught in seminars and lectures, on different topics such as Biotechnology and recycled plastics. Some examples of the materials are shown in figures 6-8.

Agro2Circular

Actividades de difusión y concienciación de la sociedad
Tema: Reciclado de plásticos

Alejandro Arribas Agüero
Departamento de I+D
CETEC

cetec
centro tecnológico
del calzado y del plástico

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838.

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Reciclado de plásticos

Reciclado

“Upcycling”

Economía circular

2

Reciclado de plásticos

SI	SI	SI	SI
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Materia orgánica (restos de comida). ✓ Material que no pueda ser reciclado (Cd's, juguetes rotos, bombillas, sartenes, cubiertos, cristales rotos...). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Botellas y envases de plástico. ✓ Envases metálicos (latas de refresco y conservas). ✓ Envases brik. ✓ Papel de aluminio y envoltorios. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Envases de vidrio (botellas, frascos o tarros). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Envases y cajas de cartón. ✓ Periódicos, libros, revistas y bolsas de papel.
<p>NO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Todo lo que pueda ser reciclado (contenedores amarillo, verde y azul). ✗ Sustancias peligrosas (baterías, pilas, medicamentos...). 	<p>NO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Envases de cartón, papel y envases de vidrio. ✗ Envases de productos contaminantes (lubricantes). ✗ Electrodomésticos o vajillas. ✗ Cubos o cajas. ✗ Cd's, cintas de vídeo, perchas, juguetes. ✗ Zapatillas o ropa. 	<p>NO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Bombillas y fluorescentes. ✗ Tarros de medicamentos. ✗ Cristal de ventanas o espejos. ✗ Vasos o copas de cristal. ✗ Tapones o corchos. ✗ Porcelana y cerámica. 	<p>NO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Papel de aluminio. ✗ Briks. ✗ Pañales, servilletas y pañuelos. ✗ Papel o cartón sucios o manchados de aceite y/o grasa.

¿Dónde reciclar?

3

9.1.1 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for primary schools:

Role-play	"The sustainable farm". Students play the role of farmers who want to turn their farm into a sustainable farm and learn about the importance of organic farming and waste management.
Scenario	"The school garden". Students play the role of farmers who want to turn their farm into a sustainable farm and learn about the importance of organic farming and waste management.
Crossword	"Sustainability in the kitchen". Students learn about the importance of buying local and organic food, reducing food waste and separating waste in the kitchen.
Slide presentation	"From plastics to bioplastics". Students learn about the importance of reducing the use of plastics and the transition to more sustainable materials such as bioplastics.
Role-play	"The park clean-up team". Students can play the role of members of a clean-up crew who want to reduce the amount of plastics in a park and learn about the importance of waste management and separation of materials.
Scenario	"The plastic-free shop". Students create and manage a small shop that sells plastic-free products and learn about the importance of reducing the use of plastics in our daily lives.
Game	"The recycling game". Students can create and manage a recycling plant and learn about the importance of circular economy and waste management.
Role-play	"The repair shop". Students can play the role of workers in a repair workshop and learn about the importance of reusing and repairing objects.
Slide presentation	"The circular economy in action". Students can learn about real examples of circular economy and how circular economy can help to solve environmental and social problems.

9.1.2 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for secondary schools:

Role Play	<p>Activity 1: students carry out a role play in which they pretend to be farmers and work in teams to design an agricultural production system that is sustainable and circular. They will have to consider aspects such as resource efficiency, waste management, reducing environmental impact and promoting biodiversity.</p> <p>Activity 2: students pretend to be a company that wants to produce sustainable and circular packaging. They will have to research different materials and technologies, analyse costs and benefits, and make decisions on which materials to use, how to design packaging, how to collect and recycle waste, among other aspects.</p>
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	<p>Activity 3: students participate in a role-play in which they pretend to be entrepreneurs who must make decisions to reduce the environmental impact of their plastic products. They must consider factors such as using recycled materials, designing more sustainable products, and implementing recycling and composting systems.</p> <p>Activity 4: students pretend to be a team working in a company, governmental organisation or CSO that wants to implement a circular economy system (examples provided by A2C). They will have to research the different aspects involved in the circular economy, such as waste management, efficient use of resources, reduction of the carbon footprint, and design a strategy that is viable and sustainable. In this way, the relevance for young people to participate in the public sphere to defend their own interests is also promoted.</p> <p>Activity 5: students participate in a role-play in which they pretend to be managers of a company and must make decisions to integrate circular economy principles into their business model. They must consider factors such as resource efficiency, sustainable product design, and the implementation of recycling and composting systems.</p>
Slide presentations	<p>Topics: regenerative agriculture, organic waste management, the economics of short marketing loops, urban agriculture, the importance of buying local and seasonal food, among others; key concepts of the circular economy in plastics, such as different types of plastics and their environmental impacts, recycling and biodegradation technologies, circular economy policies and strategies in the plastics sector, among others;</p>
Crossword	<p>Students solve a crossword puzzle featuring terms related to plastics and bioplastics, such as "biodegradable plastics", "natural polymers" and "microplastics", or related to agrifood, such as "organic farming", "crop rotation" and "local food".</p>

9.2 General considerations and the context of the circular economy

Co-design and extension of materials already developed by the partners in the framework of Task 8.3. On this regard, a general presentation on circular economy has already been prepared, as shown in figures 9-11:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838.

Figure 9 - presentation on CE 1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101036838.

1. Economía lineal vs Economía circular

2. ¿Qué es la economía circular?

La economía circular es un **modelo de producción y consumo** que implica compartir, alquilar, reutilizar, reparar, renovar y reciclar materiales y productos existentes todas las veces que sea posible para crear un valor añadido.

De esta forma, el **ciclo de vida** de los productos se extiende.

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The materials will include the topic of the sustainability paradigm, sustainable development, life cycle thinking, and what role the circular economy plays in this framework.

9.2.1 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for primary schools:

Games & Role Play	<p>Activity 1: waste sorting game. In this game, students will have to sort different types of waste into the corresponding bins (organic, plastics, paper and cardboard, glass, etc.) to understand the importance of waste separation and how it contributes to the circular economy</p> <p>Activity 2: students become a community and have to make decisions regarding waste and resource management to achieve sustainability and ecological transition. The activity will be designed to be implemented in groups.</p> <p>Activity 3: - Memory game: print out pictures related to the circular economy, such as a cardboard container, a plastic bottle, a reusable bag, etc. Place them face down and ask students to find the pairs of matching images. To make it more challenging, students can be asked to describe what makes each object 'circular'.</p> <p>Activity 4: collection of recyclable materials such as cardboard, plastic bottles, cans and paper, and asking students to create something new from these materials. You can give them a specific theme, such as 'create a new toy' or 'create a useful object for their home'.</p>
Slide presentations	<p>Presentation with pictures to explain in a clear and simple way what the circular economy is, why it is important and what its basic principles are.</p>
Crossword	<p>Crossword puzzle with terms related to the circular economy, sustainability and the ecological transition, such as “recycling”, “reuse”, “Renewable energy”, “Pollution”, etc. Students will be able to learn new terms and better understand how these concepts relate to each other.</p>

9.2.2 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for secondary schools.

Role-play	<p>Activity 1: Students play the role of different actors involved in the circular economy, such as consumers, businesses, governments and CSOs. Through the game, students can</p>
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	<p>understand how each actor affects and is affected by the circular economy system.</p> <p>Activity 2: A hypothetical scenario is presented in which students have to design a circular economy strategy for a company, city or region. Through the scenario, students can understand how the circular economy relates to sustainability and ecological transition in practice.</p>
Debate	<p>Students carry out research and discuss the advantages and disadvantages of the circular economy compared to the linear economy. They can be asked to consider different aspects, such as resource efficiency, waste reduction and job creation.</p>
Research Project	<p>Activity 1: Students conduct research on different circular economy practices and technologies, such as recycling, repair and reuse. They can present their findings in a report or presentation.</p> <p>Activity 2: Case analysis. Students analyse real cases of companies, cities or regions that have implemented circular economy practices. They can identify the challenges and opportunities they encountered and assess their impact in terms of sustainability and ecological transition</p>

9.3 The A2C results and outcomes

For the introduction of the results and outcomes of the A2C project, UVEG will coordinate with ICONS in order to ensure that the preparation of materials complies with IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) regulations.

9.3.1 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for primary schools:

Game	<p>"Agro2Circular: the road to circular economy". In this game, students become farmers and have to make decisions on how to produce, distribute and sell their products in a more sustainable and circular way. The game includes cards with information about the Agro2Circular project and other examples of circular economy in the agri-food sector.</p>
Slide presentation	<p>"Agro2Circular in the Region of Murcia". In this presentation, students will learn about the objectives and results of the Agro2Circular project in the Region of Murcia, and how circular economy practices are being implemented in the agri-food sector. The presentation will include videos, images and interactive questions to keep students interested.</p>

9.3.2 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for secondary schools.

<p>Game</p>	<p>“Agro2Circular: the road to circular economy”. In this game, students become farmers and have to make decisions on how to produce, distribute and sell their products in a more sustainable and circular way. The game includes cards with information about the Agro2Circular project and other examples of circular economy in the agri-food sector.</p>
<p>Real life scenarios</p>	<p>Present students different real-life scenarios where the circular economy is applied in the agri-food, plastic or footwear sector. Ask them to identify the environmental and economic benefits of the circular economy in each case and how they could be applied in other similar scenarios.</p>
<p>Slide presentation</p>	<p>"Agro2Circular in the Region of Murcia". In this presentation, students will learn about the objectives and results of the Agro2Circular project in the Region of Murcia, and how circular economy practices are being implemented in the agri-food sector. The presentation will include videos, images and interactive questions to keep students interested.</p>

A slideshow on the suprarecycling of plastics using Biotechnology has been already created by CETECBIO, as shown in figures 12-14:

Figure 12 - presentation on suprarecycling of plastics using Biotechnology 1

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101036838.

Figure 13 - presentation on suprarecycling of plastics using Biotechnology 2

Figure 14 - presentation on suprarecycling of plastics using Biotechnology 3

9.4 Environmental-responsive entrepreneurship: Clusters and sectoral initiatives; synergies; Academic careers, entrepreneurship and intellectual exploitation.

The materials will be developed in collaboration with UB and EURA, as they are the ones carrying out the most relevant actions of the A2C project in terms of Circular Economy Business Models and funding schemes.

9.4.1 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for primary schools:

Slide presentation	Slide presentation containing images about careers and professions related to the circular economy.
Role play	Role play game in which students play different professions related to the circular economy, such as waste pickers, green farmers, environmental engineers, etc.

9.4.2 Examples of didactic materials to be developed for secondary schools.

Research & Role play	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity 1: Students can research local businesses that use sustainable business practices and present them to the class in the form of a presentation or poster. They can then discuss how these practices could be applied in other businesses. - Activity 2: Students can form teams and create their own sustainable business. They should present a business plan that includes how they will reduce waste, use renewable resources and respect the environment in general. - Activity 3: Students can research different careers related to the circular economy, such as environmental engineering, waste management, recycling, sustainable design, etc. They can then create a brochure or presentation about these careers and share it with the class. - Activity 4: Students can interview professionals working in the circular economy, such as waste managers, sustainable designers, environmental engineers, etc. and present their findings to the class.
Slide presentation	Slide presentation containing images, graphics and explanatory text about the importance of environmentally sensitive entrepreneurship and careers and professions related to the circular economy, including information about the creation of companies that use recycled or biodegradable materials, or about the demand for professionals in the waste management or renewable energy sector.

10 Industry Mentoring Programme

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

“At regional level, PRIMA will develop an industry mentoring programme aimed at generating innovative results-oriented ideas to respond to circular business challenges, through A2C multidimensional approach.”

This document presents an outline of the mentoring programme designed by PRIMA, as well as a draft of the evaluation system proposed by UVEG. The evaluation system will be refined over the coming months.

Relation with other partners and WPs	-
Materials to be developed/ target groups	Outline of practical training activities and materials for the development of the industry mentoring programme (Target group: industry, technical personnel)

10.1 Description: aims and phases of the Mentoring Programme

The Primafrio Foundation's commitment to the Agro2circular Project is embodied in the mission to organise a mentoring programme for companies in the agri-food sector in the region to generate innovations aimed at responding to the challenges of this model, within the framework of the objectives and solutions set out in it.

This programme includes the monitoring and evaluation of the innovations generated to ensure that they are implemented, and the results obtained from them are measured, as well as providing deliverables to facilitate the dissemination of the programme in other European regions.

Face-to-face sessions where work is carried out on the basis of training and the initiation of phase B is carried out in this same training session.

One face-to-face session for the identification of challenges, generation of ideas, selection and elaboration of proposals.

- 3 to 4 online sessions (joint and by subgroups per company) to deepen the identification of actions already carried out (B) or new ideas (C).
- Participants: 3 to 5 companies, 2 to 5 people per company, to have a team of about 10/20 people.

Phase A - Training

Face-to-face training session, suitable for the agri-food sector, on the concepts and proposals of the Circular Economy, customised to the field of activity of the A2C project, although there will be examples from other fields. It is the starting point for the subsequent phases proposed.

This session requires a previous activity of preparation of the material taking into account the A2C project as a whole, with the support of the participants of the project who have been developing the researches that give solutions to the challenges raised.

The expected number of attendees is about 10/20 people, belonging to 3 to 5 companies.

Estimated duration of the activity:

- Preparation: 2 weeks
- Training session: 4 hours

Phase B- Actions already implemented

The aim of this phase is to identify actions already carried out by the participating companies that respond to the approach proposed by the circular economy in order to facilitate the understanding of the concepts of the model and to motivate the participants by confirming that they are certainly already on the way.

The attending teams, who will have participated in the training, will analyse, within the projects already implemented, which of them could respond to this model. Through working meetings with the monitor, they will assess whether these projects really meet their criteria. For these meetings, the participants will be grouped into two subgroups, taking into account their position in the value chain.

Estimated duration of the activity:

- Face-to-face session: 3 hours (same day as the training).
- Complete the information: two weeks, including online sessions (one per subgroup and one group session).

Phase C - Generation of innovation proposals

This area of collaboration is expected to generate proposals for innovation projects that respond to the two business challenges of the A2C project, the implementation of which would imply that the participating companies incorporate the Circular Economy as a model, with the economic, environmental and social advantages that this model provides.

The activities planned in this area of collaboration are as follows:

- Workshop with the teams to generate and select innovative ideas.

It would be a workshop of about four hours, requiring prior preparation by the monitor and a professional expert in the technologies and solutions proposed by the A2C project.

- Online sessions, two for each of the two subgroups (grouping by similarity of ideas), to complete the selection of ideas and elaboration of project proposals, plus an online session with the whole group to summarise the project proposals.

The result would be one or more proposals with cost, effort, impact, risks, etc. to develop the selected ideas.

Phase D – Follow up and Evaluation

Periodic monitoring and evaluation activities will be carried out (to be determined according to A2C project requirements) to verify the progress in the implementation of the ideas generated and the progression in the transition to the Circular Economy model of the companies involved in the mentoring programme.

It is estimated that this monitoring will be done online for a period of about three months, with a dedication of the trainer to attend approximately one monthly meeting per subgroup, one group meeting and one meeting with the project coordinator.

The duration of the collaboration is estimated at 3 and a half months for phases A to D, plus the period of monitoring and evaluation activities for about three months to monitor the implementation of the projects in the companies participating in the mentoring programme.

10.2 Evaluation System Draft

There are 3 major impact evaluation models of training in organisations: the Kirkpatrick, Philips & Wade models¹¹. Here, we propose the utilisation of the Kirkpatrick model since it has clear assessment steps (reaction, learning, behaviour and results) so it is easier to avoid getting bogged down by unforeseen events. However, as other evaluation mode, Kirkpatrick model has difficulties to measure ROI (return of investment) because it's a multi-causal phenomenon by tangible and intangible factors¹².

Figure 15 shows the 4 evaluation levels of the Kirkpatrick model:

¹¹ P. Pineda Herrero, "Evaluación del impacto de la formación de las organizaciones," *Educar*, no. 27, pp. 119-133, 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://raco.cat/index.php/Educar/article/view/20737>

¹² M. P. Schroeder-Strong, B. Schreiber, and W. Bennett, "A methodology for projecting the return on investment of training technologies," *Military Psychology*, 2022, doi: 10.1080/08995605.2022.2050164

Figure 15 - Kirkpatrick model

The following table shows what is proposed to be analysed and how do we propose to collect the information:

Analysis level	Methods of data collection
Reaction: how participants feel about training	Questionnaire or Likert scale 1-5. At the end of the course.
Learning: how participants increase their skill/knowledge	Focus group, questionnaire. During the course or at the end.
Behaviour: what changes have occurred on participants	Questionnaire, Interview/Observation, During the course and 3-12 months after the course.
Results: improvement in the production process	In production process indicators as: - Reducing losses in production:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Material recycling- Circular economy performance- ROI (Return on investment) <p>Questionnaire, interview and focus group. 3-24 months after the course.</p>
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11 Good practice directory for Circular Economy in the agrifood sector

T.8.6 (WP8) Grant Agreement:

“AGRO will design a survey pool hosted within the stakeholders’ platform targeting stakeholders in Murcia. From the data collected through these surveys (T.7.4) AGRO will elaborate an initial individual evaluation about the circular economy situation of the surveys’ participants which will be integrated into D.8.6. Agro will also elaborate a good practice directory for Circular Economy in the agrifood sector, which will be visible through the project’s web tool.”

Therefore, the deliverable, version 8.7, will contain both the results of the survey generated at T.7.4 and the directory of good practices.

Relation with other partners and WPs	<p>WP7 (KVC, UVEG, TCA, LPK)- Task 7.1.2 Community-based innovation schemes. KVC in collaboration with UVEG, TCA and LPK will analyse other successful community-based innovation schemes in order to further deliver within the A2C systemic model, together with the results of our pilot action, recommendations for fostering public engagement in circular economy initiatives/projects.</p> <p>WP7 (AGRO, PROEX & PRIMA) – Task 7.4 Social and economic analysis (M5 to M36). AGRO will design a survey pool hosted within the stakeholders’ platform targeting stakeholders in Murcia. PROEX & PRIMA will provide the socio-economic view from the territorial agrifood sector. Following dimensions at territorial/community level will be evaluated and quantified: a) production and jobs creation; impact on employment; b) economic security and impact on the redistribution of prosperity and reduction of poverty; c) involvement and participation of citizens traditionally excluded from the decision-making processes; d) Equity, social justice and inclusiveness; e) social design and value attributed co-designed solutions tailored to community-specific contexts and conditions; f) other potential impacts of the A2C systemic solution (e.g. quality of life improvement, material circumstances of communities). Then, acceptance will be analysed and presented in-light of the previous results.</p>
Materials to be developed/ target groups	Directory of good practices to be uploaded on the project website.

In November 2019, the President of the European Commission presented the EU Green Pact, a plan that includes fifty concrete actions to combat climate change, which aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent in the year 2050. The objective of this 'EU Green Deal' is for Europe to have a clean economy, with zero emissions, and to protect our natural habitat to improve the well-being of people and companies and to take the lead in climate action throughout the planet. In addition, at the national and regional level we find the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy and the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia 2017-2030.

For all these reasons, it is important to publicise and value good circular economy practices promoted by citizens, civil society organisations, companies and other sectors, in areas such as the prevention of food waste that is part of the Agro2Circular project, funded by the European Union.

The agri-food industry is one of the sectors most exposed to sustainability challenges and opportunities, due to direct dependence and action on natural resources, which is why it is considered a high-impact industry. Sustainability, in all its aspects: social, economic and environmental, is a fundamental parameter for companies. The Agro2Circular project planned actions to help and raise awareness in the agri-food sector of the need to apply the principles of Circular Economy.

In this context, the partner AGROFOOD has defined a line of work to develop a Directory that displays Good Circular Economy Practices, both those proposed in the development of the A2C project, and others considered example of success that are known through a open search at the National level, or through the exchange of information with stakeholders involved in the project. Below is the proposed Directory index to help circularise the economy and face the challenge of limited natural resources.

11.1 INDEX DIRECTORY GOOD PRACTICES CIRCULAR ECONOMY – REGION OF MURCIA SCOPE

1. Introduction and objective of the Directory of Good Practices
2. The agri-food sector, the plastic packaging sector and the Circular Economy
3. Current situation. Policies and aid in the Region of Murcia aimed at Circular Economy
4. Selection methodology of Good Practices in Circular Economy
 - a. Valuation criteria
 - b. Contents presented in tabs.
5. Sheets of Good Practices implemented.
 - a. Agri-food and nutraceutical sector
 - b. plastic sector
 - c. cosmetic sector
6. Agro2Circular. A Circular Economy Strategy for the Region of Murcia
7. Valorisation of agri-food by-products. Sustainable technologies for obtaining compounds of interest and plastic recycling.
 - a. Sheets of potential techniques and protocols

8. Conclusions
9. Bibliography

Each one of the sections of the proposed index has been selected with a clear objective of being a quick visualisation of the current situation and the future potential of the revaluation of agri-food by-products and other waste.

A. An Introduction is contemplated to situate the reader of the document by exposing the sources of information for the detection of Good Practices.

B. A brief exposition of the current situation of the Circular Economy Concept linked to the agri-food sector and its auxiliary sector of plastic packaging is contemplated. The demands that the sector has in accordance with current legislation and the consumer. A global vision.

C. Given that the Agro2Circular project has established a Circular Economy Strategy for the Region of Murcia, it is contemplated to include a list of policies and aid with a detailed vision of the Region of Murcia.

D. Subsequently, the work methodology for the selection and presentation of the results of detected Good Practices will be exposed.

On the one hand, the selection assessment criteria will be indicated based on:

- Key results: main achievements (environmental, economic and social) obtained thanks to the implementation of the Good Practice. (40%)
- Solutions to challenges that the entity responsible for the Good Practice has faced to implement it. (30%)
- Scope of action of the Good Practice – i) agri-food sector; ii) nutraceutical, iii) plastic, iv) cosmetic, v) other. (20 %)
- Link to SDG commitments. (10%)

On the other hand, the content of the tabs designed with the following information will be presented:

- Name of the Good Practice
- Location of the Good Practice
- Objective of the Good Practice
- Description and results of the Good Practice
- Advantages and disadvantages of the implementation of the Good Practice
- Entity responsible for Good Practice
- Representative image

E. The Good Practices detected and already implemented at the National level will be included one by one, which will be placed in a ranking according to the score obtained in the evaluation criteria. In addition, they will be classified according to the scope of action with the greatest link to the revaluation itself in the agri-food entity or in other industries.

F. The Agro2Circular project will be presented, indicating a brief description of the tasks of WPs 2, 3 and 6, as well as the partners involved in them.

G. The results with the potential to be considered Good Practices will be displayed in sheets (similar to those in section D mentioned above). It will be taken into account to include work protocols.

H. Finally, some conclusions and more relevant bibliographical references will be included.

